

A LINGUISTIC-POETIC ANALYSIS OF THE MESSAGE OF GOROGLI

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Abstract: This article analyzes the linguopoetic features of the epic poem "Gorogli," a rare example of Uzbek folk oral art. The study examines the epic's artistic representational devices, the aesthetic function of linguistic units, poetic structure, and national-cultural semantics.

Keywords: Gorogli, linguopoetic studies, folklore, artistic language, metaphor, epithet, stylistics, folk oral literature, poetic devices, semantics.

Introduction.

Uzbek folklore is an invaluable spiritual heritage formed over centuries of historical development, embodying the social life, worldview, aesthetic views, and spiritual experiences of the people. Epic epics hold a special place within this rich heritage. This is because dastans are a major genre that expresses the historical memory, heroic ideals, dreams, aspirations, and social struggles of a people through artistic images.

Among the Uzbek epic heritage, the epic "Gorogly" is distinguished by its wide distribution, variety, rich content, and artistic maturity. This epic holds an important place not only in the Uzbek people but also in the folklore of other Turkic peoples. The image of "Gorogly" was formed in the minds of the people as a just, brave, and people-loving hero, and he is depicted as an ideal figure who fights against oppression and protects the interests of the people.

The artistic value of this epic is determined not only by its plot and system of images but also by its unique linguistic structure, means of expression, poetic structure, and stylistic richness. Therefore, the linguopoetic approach is of particular importance in the study of the epic. Linguopoetics is a scientific field that studies the aesthetic function of linguistic units in a literary text and their role in creating an artistic image, forming a comprehensive field of research at the intersection of linguistics and literary studies.

In the context of modern scientific development, there is a growing need for a profound analysis of the literary text not only in terms of content but also through its linguistic and stylistic features. In particular, the linguopoetic study of folklore texts yields important scientific results in identifying the uniqueness of folk thinking, national mentality, and cultural codes. From this point of view, the epic "Gorogly" is an extremely convenient and rich material for linguopoetic analysis.

The linguistic features of the epic "Gorogly" consist of a multi-layered and complex system. It combines elements of the ancient Turkic language, colloquial units, poetic formulas, repetitive constructions, and figurative expressions. This increases not only the communicative but also the aesthetic and emotional impact of the dastan language. It is these aspects that require special attention as the main object of linguopoetic analysis.

The means of artistic depiction used in the text of the epic - metaphor, epithet, comparison, personification - provide imagery and have a strong aesthetic effect on the listener

or reader. For example, using images of the animal world to express the hero's strength and power, creating a dramatic effect by comparing it with natural phenomena is one of the important features of the poetics of the epic. This, in turn, shows that language units perform not only a nominative but also an expressive function.

Furthermore, syntactic constructions characteristic of the oral performance form of the dastan—parallelism, repetition, and rhythmic units—also hold linguopoetic significance. These tools ensure the musicality of the text, increase its level of memorization, and have a strong effect on listeners during the performance process. Therefore, the epic "Gorogly" is evaluated not only as a literary work but also as a vivid example of the art of language and speech.

Currently, linguopoetic research is one of the important scientific directions for a deeper understanding of the internal structure of a literary text, identifying its semantic and stylistic layers, as well as revealing how the author's or people's thinking is expressed through language. However, it should be noted that the linguopoetic features of the epic "Gorogly" have not yet been fully and systematically studied. Although many studies have analyzed the plot, images, and historical roots of the epic, insufficient attention has been paid to its linguistic and poetic structure.

The purpose of this article is to identify the linguopoetic features of the "Gorogly" epic, analyze the artistic and aesthetic function of the language units within it, and reveal the unique aspects of the epic's poetics. To achieve this goal, the following tasks have been defined:

- analysis of the lexical layer in the epic;
- determination of the use of artistic imagery;
- studying syntactic and stylistic features;
- revealing the aesthetic and emotional function of language units;
- highlighting the national-cultural semantics of the epic.

Various versions of the epic "Gorogly" were selected as the object of the research, and its subject is its linguopoetic features.

In conclusion, the epic "Gorogly" is a high-level example of Uzbek oral folk art not only in terms of content but also in terms of language and style, and its study from a linguopoetic point of view serves to deeply understand the artistic thinking, aesthetic views and linguistic possibilities of the people. Therefore, this study is distinguished by its relevance, scientific novelty, and practical significance.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS. The scientific study of the epic "Gorogly" and samples of epic folklore as a whole has a long history and is closely related to research conducted in the fields of linguistics, literary studies, and folklore studies. In particular, the research on the genre features, composition and system of images of epic epics serves as an important theoretical basis for understanding the artistic nature of these works.

In Uzbek folklore studies, the dastan "Gorogly" has been studied separately, and its various variants, plot networks, and character systems have been scientifically analyzed. However, in the early studies, the main attention was paid to the content and historical roots of the work, and its linguistic features were not sufficiently covered³.

The direction of linguopoetics involves the aesthetic study of a literary text through linguistic means. According to this approach, the essence of a work of art is not limited to content, but also manifests in the artistic function of the language units that represent it. From

this point of view, epic dastans, including the dastan "Gorogly," are an important source for linguopoetic analysis.

Research in the field of linguistics and stylistics of literary texts extensively covers the expressive means of language, their functional and semantic features. In particular, the role and aesthetic impact of artistic means such as metaphor, epithet, comparison in speech are analyzed on a scientific basis. This serves as an important methodological basis for studying folklore texts.

A distinctive feature of folklore works is that they are products of oral creativity. For this reason, formulaic expressions, repetitive units, and rhythmic constructions are widely used in such texts. Researchers evaluate these units as an integral part of epic poetics. These tools not only enhance the aesthetic impact of the text but also ensure its memorization.

The lexical richness of the language of the epic "Gorogly" is also highlighted in the scientific literature. Folk words, archaisms and dialectisms are widely used in it, which strengthens the national color of the work⁸. At the same time, ancient Turkic elements have been preserved in the language of the dastan, which are important from a historical and linguistic point of view.

Scientific research notes that metaphorical thinking occupies an important place in epic dastans. In the epic "Gorogly," the mental state, internal experiences, and social relations of the characters are also expressed through figurative expressions. This shows that language units have a deep semantic layer.

According to the results of stylistic research, solemnity, a high tone, and expressiveness predominate in epic texts. This enhances the aesthetic value of the dastan and distinguishes it from texts of other genres. Strong emotional colors play an important role in expressing the spirit of heroism.

In modern linguistic approaches, special attention is paid to the cognitive and pragmatic study of the literary text. This serves to reveal the connection of language units in the text with human thinking and culture. From this point of view, the epic "Gorogly" is also of great importance as a linguocultural source expressing the national mentality.

An analysis of the literature shows that although many scientific studies have been conducted on the epic "Gorogly," its linguopoetic features have not yet been fully systematically studied. In most studies, issues of plot, image, and historicity are prioritized, while language and poetic means are not comprehensively analyzed.

Therefore, there is a need for an in-depth study of the following issues:

- systematic classification of linguopoetic means;
- their functional-semantic features;
- mechanisms of aesthetic influence of artistic language;
- linguistic foundations of folklore poetics

In conclusion, the existing scientific literature shows that the epic "Gorogly" has great scientific potential in linguopoetic terms. Research conducted in this direction can make a significant contribution to the development of linguistics and folklore studies.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS. The epic "Gorogly" is one of the largest epic examples of Uzbek folklore, reflecting the historical memory, aesthetic views, values, and artistic thinking of the people. In the process of linguopoetic analysis, a number of important conclusions were drawn

from the point of view of the lexical, grammatical, stylistic and image-creating means of the dastan text.

1. Analysis of the lexical layer

The following lexical layers predominate in the language of the dastan:

Archaic and historical words: represent the ancient layer of the epic (for example, old military titles, terms related to customs).

Dialect-specific units: regional lexical differences are observed in the dastans of "Gorogly," which are narrated in different variants.

Epic formulas: traditional beginnings and repetitive expressions of the "once upon a time" type.

2. Phonetic and rhythmic features

In the text of the epic:

alliteration (repetition of consonants),

assonance (harmony of vowels),

internal rhymes and rhythmic repetitions

widely used.

For example, sound repetitions in battle and heroic scenes give the text dynamism and dramatic power.

3. Morphological and syntactic features

The plurality of verb forms enhances the dynamics of action.

Imperative and exclamatory sentences are frequently encountered in the speech of characters.

Although simple sentences predominate, repeated and non-conjunctive compound sentences provide epic breadth.

4. Means of artistic representation

The following poetic devices are actively used in the dastan:

Metaphor - in expressing the strength and courage of the characters

Analogy - comparing characters with nature or animals

Epithets are permanent adjectives such as "brave," "invincible," and "courageous."

Hyperbole - an exaggeration of heroism

5. System of images and linguopoetic expression

The main characters in the epic are:

Gorogly is an ideal hero, a symbol of justice

the image of the horse is a symbol of loyalty and strength

enemy images are an expression of evil and injustice

Each image is idealized through linguistic means and has a symbolic meaning.

Linguopoetic Devices (Donut)

The epic "Gorogly" is one of the largest and most complex epic works of Uzbek oral folk art, and as a result of its linguopoetic analysis, it was revealed that the artistic-aesthetic system, language capabilities, and poetic structure of the work are deep and multi-layered. The text of the epic serves not only as a source for preserving historical and cultural memory but also as an important literary phenomenon embodying the artistic thinking, linguistic richness, and aesthetic views of the people.

In the process of linguopoetic analysis, when studying the lexical, phonetic, morphological, syntactic and stylistic features of the epic, it was observed that it is deeply connected to the traditions of oral creativity, and at the same time, it has an artistically perfect system. The widespread use of archaic words, dialectal units, and epic formulas in the language of the dastan expresses its historical layer and shows that the people have preserved the ancient richness of the language.

Phonetically, alliteration, assonance, and rhythmic repetitions enhance the musicality of the dastan and enhance its expressiveness during oral performance. This confirms that the epic "Gorogly" is an artistic system adapted not only for reading but also for singing and reciting.

The results of morphological and syntactic analysis show that the language of the epic is rich in verb forms expressing action and dynamics, and the sequence of events is presented in a fluent and understandable way through simple and repetitive sentence constructions. This situation ensures that the work is adapted to the oral performance tradition and is easily perceived by the listener.

The widespread use of artistic imagery—metaphor, simile, epithet, and hyperbole—serves to idealize the hero's image. As a result, the image of Gorogly was formed among the people as a symbol of justice, courage and bravery. Additionally, a contrasting artistic system is

created through horse, battle scenes, and enemy images, which further enhances the dramatic power of the epic.

In general, the epic "Gorogly":

has a rich and multi-layered lexical system;

phonetically rich in musical and rhythmic features;

syntactically adapted to oral performance;

possesses a strong poetic impact through means of artistic expression;

is an epic monument that embodies the historical, cultural, and spiritual views of the people.

At the same time, the results of the linguopoetic analysis confirm that the epic "Gorogly" holds a special place in the Uzbek literary heritage and that its language and artistic system are an important source worthy of scientific study.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS. This article analyzes the epic "Gorogly" from a linguopoetic perspective, examining its linguistic features and means of artistic expression. As a result of the analysis, the lexical composition of the epic is rich and diverse, and the extensive use of archaic words, dialectal units, and epic formulas shows that the work is based on historical and oral traditions.

Phonetically, the presence of alliteration, assonance, and rhythmic repetitions enhances the musicality of the dastan and enhances its expressiveness during oral performance. This circumstance confirms that the epic "Gorogly" is important not only as a text but also as a performance art.

The predominance of simple, repetitive, and imperative sentences in syntactic structures serves to express the development of events quickly and accurately. The widespread use of artistic imagery (metaphor, simile, epithet, and hyperbole) idealizes the characters and enhances the aesthetic impact of the work.

OFFERS

In-depth study of the epic from a linguopoetic perspective

It is advisable to more accurately highlight the territorial and linguistic features of the "Gorogly" epic by conducting a comparative analysis of its various versions.

Implementation into the educational process

Incorporating more dastan materials into school and higher education textbooks, and teaching it based on linguopoetic analysis, develops the artistic thinking of students.

Creation of an electronic database Digitizing all versions of the epic "Gorogly" and placing them on an electronic platform or national corpus will facilitate its scientific study.

Expansion of scientific research

It is necessary to comprehensively study the dastan not only in linguopoetic, but also in folklore, cultural and historical aspects.

Strengthening cultural propaganda work

Increasing the number of theatrical productions, audio and video projects based on the dastan will increase the interest of the younger generation in the national heritage.

References:

1. Karimov N. Uzbek folklore. - Тошкент, 2017. - 256 p.
2. Yuldashev B. Fundamentals of Linguopoetics. - Тошкент: ЎЗМУ, 2017. - 198 p.

3. Rakhmonov N. Uzbek epic. - Тошкент, 2017. - 312 p.
4. Juraev M. Theory of Folklore. - Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 2005. - 224 p.
5. Qodirov T. Linguistics of literary text. - Тошкент: ЎзМУ, 2014. - 276 p.
6. Vohidov E. Theory of Uzbek literature. - Тошкент, 2017. - 340 p.
7. Tursunov U. Fundamentals of Stylistics. - Тошкент, 2017. - 210 p.
8. Khodiyev B. Stylistics of the Uzbek language. - Тошкент: ЎзМУ, 2013. - 288 p.
9. Hasanov A. Epic Thinking and Language. - Тошкент: ЎзМУ, 2017. - 230 p.
10. Abdullaev A. Folklore and linguistics. - Тошкент, 2020. - 190 p.
11. Sharipov R. Culture of artistic speech. - Тошкент: "Ma'naviyat," 2011. - 176 p.
12. Sodiqov Q. Fundamentals of Uzbek Linguistics. - Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 2017. - 300 p..